

Walking in Troubled Times in Anna Burns' *Milkman*

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Abstract

In her Booker-prize winning novel *Milkman* (2018), Anna Burns traces the journey of “middle sister”, her young and witty protagonist who loves to read while walking in the streets of a city that resembles Belfast in the 1970s during the Troubles. The novel critiques the political situation in Northern Ireland through spatial imagery: Moving through the city space is a rebellious act in the embattled zone controlled by the paramilitaries. The unnamed protagonist’s walks through deserted streets are her form of resistance and her silent but effective rebellion against the tyrannical and chauvinist regime is expressed in her desire to walk *and* read, to be propelled forwards and to move freely in an urban space controlled by sexist and conservative ideology and, at the same time, through her reading, escape into an imaginary space that is different from the tense political situation of late 1970s Belfast.

Walking and crossing boundaries are not mere metaphors but transcend the limits of the text as they invite the reader to re-think their own walking/reading patterns as possible outlets in times of crisis. The experience of walking in urban space may lead to a re-evaluation of the city as a cultural and political space and walking might develop into a socio-political discourse that engages with urban space in favour of the citizens and communities. This article discusses the cultural and political significance of walking and reading as charted in Burns’ novel *Milkman* and proposes a re-thinking of walking as a democratic practice in times of crisis.

Keywords

novel, walking, city, urban space, crisis

In her Booker-prize winning novel *Milkman* (2018), Anna Burns traces the journey of “middle sister”, her young and witty protagonist who loves to read while walking in the streets of a city that resembles Belfast in the 1970s during The Troubles¹. The novel critiques the political situation in Northern Ireland through her walking protagonist: Moving through the city space signifies her freedom in the embattled zone controlled by the paramilitaries on the one hand and the state on the other. Her resistance and her silent but effective rebellion against the tyrannical and chauvinist regime is expressed in her desire to walk *and* read, to be propelled forwards and to move freely in an urban space controlled by sexist and conservative ideology and, at the same time, through her reading, escape into an imaginary space that is different from the tense political situation of late 1970s Belfast. Walking is a form of freedom in the novel, especially for women as walking is regarded as a “shady business”. Her gender makes the protagonist extremely vulnerable to the violence in the streets as well as the threats from the dubious character enigmatically called the milkman.

But, she insists on walking and reading and, by committing to the streets,² defies any normative gender roles with their demand for conformity. Her commitment to the streets and to walking in the context of a city in crisis helps to formulate a strategic discourse for walking. One might argue that the experience of walking in urban space leads to a re-evaluation of the city as a cultural and political sphere and may evolve into a socio-political discourse that engages with the citizens’ and communities’ needs³. This article discusses the cultural and political significance of walking and reading as charted in Burns’ novel *Milkman* and propose a re-thinking of walking as a democratic practice in times of crisis.

Theories of Urban Walking

First, a re-thinking of walking needs to consider the figure of the flâneur and the flâneuse as key figures in understanding the individual and the city. Recently, the figure of the flâneur has been re-discovered in studies on the contemporary urban experience. Famous for his keen observation of city life, the flâneur helps “translating the chaotic and fragmentary city into an understandable and familiar space” (Parsons 3). In their study, Vila-Cabanes and Bock attest indeed a pervasiveness to the figure of the flâneur in contemporary theory and culture. They claim that the flâneur is both “a topic in artistic production and also a paradigm for the interpretation of urban existence” (Vila-Cabanes and Bock 9). As a paradigm for interpretation, the flâneur can serve at least two purposes: Our attention is focussed on the observation and the perception of city life. And,

¹ The violent conflict in Northern Ireland that lasted from 1969 until 2007 is commonly referred to as The Troubles.

² In *Milkman*, the young female narrator showcases an urge to re-take the street and, as Solnit aptly states, this might be understood as a democratic act: “The highest ideal of democracy—that everyone can participate in making their own life and the life of the community. And the street is democracy’s greatest arena, the place where ordinary people can speak, unsegregated by walls, unmediated by those in more power” (215-6).

³ Currently, the effects of a discursive shift can be seen as cities are meeting the new challenge by re-assigning city space and opening up streets to pedestrians (Vanderbilt) due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

secondly, the urban experience is translated into narrative in the flâneur's account of his walks.

Even though the flâneur has been traditionally seen as male, he also had a complementary figure and a counterpart in the marginal rag-picker who, in Parsons's study, is silenced by the more dominant and elitist figure of the flâneur. It is interesting to note how male and female experiences of the city differ in the analogy of flâneur versus rag-picker:

Corresponding to these structures are different types of flâneur; the authoritative architect with his panoramic blueprint and the marginal rag-picker with his city rubbish. The aim of the former is to ignore, silence, and erase the latter. The tension between valorization of the ordered, planned, and mapped, and the marginal, forgotten, and past, runs throughout the urban representations in this story, women notably taking up the latter perspective in their wanderings in the city streets. (Parsons 10)

Women walk the city, as this study proposes, as marginal citizens who are ignored, silenced and erased. But women also form a distinct relationship to the city and experience urban walking differently. Female pedestrians are, according to Parsons, closely bound to the "refuse objects of everyday life rather than [with] monumental history", and they acquire a "connective relationship with the city in which the urban landscape is regarded as a palimpsest of layered time" (Parsons 10). The flâneuse, by implication, is immersed in the urban experience, to such an extent that it is formative of her identity (Parsons 7)⁴. Therefore, I will argue that the figure of the flâneuse and her meanderings through the city, as both physical as well as narrative movement, might be a key to understanding the experience and significance of urban walking.

If one considers walking as an active engagement with urban space, and draws a connection between walking and narrative, one will find the act of walking and the act of writing closely connected. As Solnit suggests, the writer, the solitary figure, can indulge in walking and thinking to come up with ideas for their written work. She describes Rousseau's walking, for examples, as a "chosen mode of being because within a walk he is able to live in thought and reverie, to be self-sufficient, and thus to survive the world he feels has betrayed him" (Solnit 22). On the one hand, walking as a pastime fosters literary creativity. And, on the other hand, walking itself is similar to writing. Solnit claims that

[a]s a literary structure, the recounted walk encourages digression and association, in contrast to the stricter form of a discourse or the chronological progression of a biographical or historical narrative. (Solnit 22)

Therefore, the walk provides a structure for narrative texts that defies linearity and pure progression. Rather, the walking narrator captures her experience as a phenomenon of movement without form, perception without an authoritative perspective. Different from

⁴ Parsons further specifies, "I have concentrated on those women for whom the city operates as not just as setting or image, but as a constituent of identity, and how translate the experience of urban space into their narrative form" (Parsons 7).

the figure of the distant observer, the flâneur, the walking narrator, is a figure that is engaged and co-creative with the environment that she describes. According to Solnit, Joyce and Woolf translate walking in the city into a narrative mode, namely, the stream of consciousness, in which “the jumble of thoughts and recollections of their protagonists unfolds best during walks” (Solnit 22)⁵. The stream of consciousness certainly mirrors walking as it takes up different paths of thoughts, turns attention to different ideas that seem to appear along the way. Apart from the fact that the walk as a type of progression through the city space serves as an apt metaphor for the cognitive processes revealed in the stream of consciousness narrative, it is a mode of narrative that defies the more structured and linear progressions of traditional plots.

The fact that the walking individual is engaged and co-creative, traces unforeseen paths through the city and might translate this into thought, brings up the question of the subversive potential of walking. According to DeCerteau, the individual walker appropriates social practices and thus resists dominant discourses on normative social behaviour. In their “pedestrian speech acts” (97), according to DeCerteau, “[w]alking affirms, suspects, tries out, transgresses, respects, etc. the trajectories it ‘speaks’” (99). The space that is thus described by the walking individual is inscribed into the texture the city while experiencing it and, by implication, the perception of the city changes. When this happens, there is great potential for a change towards a more democratic city, one in which walking can be freely practiced and the pedestrian is unhindered in their explorations. The city might be thus re-written by the walker as a space of creativity and self-expression rather than a place of social restrictions and boundaries.

However, in the particular context of *The Troubles* as portrayed in Anna Burns’s *Milkman*, re-writing the city seems rather like a utopian idea. The social restrictions and political divisions in the novel are certainly rigid and the protagonist and her family suffer from the tense climate. The Northern Ireland that is described in the novel is terrorized by the paramilitary sections and their clandestine activities against the Protestant state, on the one hand, and the measures of the state to suppress any open nationalist rebellion, on the other. At the heart of the conflict lies the struggle between the Catholic and Protestant communities and the resulting divisions of the city: both physical and social divisions. This imposed and rigid separation of Northern Irish communities creates boundaries that curb individual movement of the physical and social kind. The city is thus inscribed with the political divisions and showcases how powerful and oppressive political ideologies are manifest in the very material cityscape. As Macauley suggests,

[i]f we follow walkers through city and suburban place, we might begin to observe the implicit cultural politics at work in various orders of ambulation. The control and maintenance of space and place, the organization of speed and pace, and the erection or transgression of

⁵ Solnit suggest that “[t]his kind of unstructured, associative thinking is the kind most often connected to walking, and it suggests walking as not an analytical but an improvisational act. Rousseau’s *Reveries* are one of the first portraits of this relationship between thinking and walking” (Solnit 22).

community ideas of citizenship or race are instances of such phenomena.
(Macauley 4)

Walkers in the city thus uncover the hidden regulation and control over space and, more specifically, movement in space. Once the walking individual enters public space they become a citizen. This is in itself problematic in the novel *Milkman* since the fractioned society of Northern Ireland glorifies the separate communities - Catholic versus Protestant - instead of allowing for a democratic notion of citizenship. Therefore, Anna Burns' walking protagonist and narrator in *Milkman* poses a challenge to the sectarian fragmentation that is revealed in the spatial layout of the city.

In the novel, walking is, I will argue, an act of democratic agency and expression of freedom. But, at the same time, the democratic agency and freedom might be curbed by political ideology as well as social norms. The question, who restricts movement in the city and why, is a pertinent one. Undoubtedly, there are instances in which walking is circumscribed by ideological boundaries and crossing those boundaries can be part of a democratic endeavour. DeCerteau's ideas of walking the city as 'writing the city' helps to further clarify who crosses boundaries and who establishes them. In his theory, DeCerteau posits that it is the walker's movement that in fact 'creates' the city space. In this way, the city is produced by the walkers many walks and paths. These walks all becomes part of manifold narratives of the city and therefore the walkers are the story-tellers of city life.

Walking as Freedom in Anna Burns' *Milkman*: Crossing Political and Spatial Boundaries

As has been noted by early reviewers of the novel, Burns paints an image of an oppressive and violent society but without giving a precise and factual context. Even though there are references to the political situation of Northern Ireland in the seventies and the setting undoubtedly resembles Belfast, the novel's fictional world remains unspecific and indefinite. Instead Burns' narrator witnesses "the oppressiveness of tribalism, of conformism, of religion, of patriarchy, of living with widespread distrust and permanent fear" (Kilroy). Suggesting that the reason for the indeterminacy and vagueness might be the genre of the novel, Hutton claims that *Milkman* is a *Bildungsroman* which centres on the coming-of-age of the protagonist rather than explores the political intricacies and processes of oppression in the particular context of Northern Ireland⁶. The focus undoubtedly lies on the protagonist and her story as she is struggling with an ever increasing state of oppression and fear. Her narrative style is unique and is embellished with the use of neologisms and idiosyncratic language. Hutton notes that "the lexical choices Burns makes enable her to communicate the character and mentality of 'middle sister', and to deconstruct the mentalities and structures of Northern Irish society as it was before the Good Friday agreement" (Hutton 358).

⁶ Hutton states that "the impact of *Milkman* stretches well beyond that initial and foundational context, and invites readers who may pay little attention to the specific and rooted historicity of the setting. *Milkman* is a *Bildungsroman* which focuses, in the end, on how middle sister resolves her difficulties and develops" (Hutton 366).

But, apart from the lexical choices of the narrator, her desire to walk and read in this particular political situation is an expression her freedom. The novel tells the story of eighteen-year old middle sister who navigates between the demands of her family, her relationship with a boy she refers to as “maybe-boyfriend” and the threats of a paramilitary officer who is dubbed “milkman”. The unnamed town that she lives in can easily be identified as Belfast in the 1970s. In the segregated city, armed violence is experienced on a daily basis and the narrator’s vivid descriptions of the conflict contributes to an impression of The Troubles that does not take sides but depicts the fight between the Catholic and Protestant communities as well as the struggle for power between the Irish State forces and the republican paramilitary groups. In the midst of this situation, the narrator renders her personal experience with Northern Irish sectarianism and the everyday violence on the streets of Belfast. It is epitomized in the figure of the milkman and her response to him has great significance for our understanding of the role of walking as an expression of freedom. The true meaning of her reading-while-walking becomes apparent once the milkman enters the scene:

He appeared one day, driving up in one of his cars as I was walking along reading *Ivanhoe*. Often I would walk along reading books. I didn’t see anything wrong with this but it became something else to be added as further proof against me. ‘Reading-while-walking’ was definitely on the list. (3)

The narrator interprets her actions here as if from an outside perspective when she states that it is “added as further proof against me”, as being “on the list”. Therefore, her community’s views and norms are apparent in their rejection of her walking. On the one hand, walking itself has the allure of freedom. On the other hand, as Solnit suggests

[u]rban walking has always been a shadier business, easily turning into soliciting, cruising, promenading, shopping, rioting, protesting, skulking, loitering, and other activities that, however enjoyable, hardly have the high moral tone of nature appreciation. (Solnit 174)

The “shadier business” of middle sister’s walking is the reason for becoming a social outcast and as such she seems a likelier and more helpless victim of the milkman’s pursuit. Her defiance of normative social behaviour in the context of the conservative ideals of her community makes her more vulnerable to the threats of the milkman. But she does not succumb to the pressures from both her community and the milkman; she keeps up her reading-while-walking.

In the course of the novel, she is repeatedly warned against the dangerous consequences of her reading – while-walking. Her brother-in-law, for examples, attempts to dissuade her from her persistent walking habits:

Not surprising either, he ran on, for as I’ve been saying, sister, you’re not vigilant as evidenced in particular by this reading-while-walking. I saw you with my own eyes last Wednesday night-time committing social insanity by entering the area completely and dangerously blind to the lower forces and influences - your head down, the tiniest of reading-torches shining on your pages. Nobody does that. (61)

He calls her pedestrian rebellion “social insanity” and calls her “dangerously blind to the lower forces and influences” suggesting that she might perceive any threats if she were more vigilant instead of immersed in the fictions of her books. Reading-while-walking is, by the narrator, established as her very individual approach to the political situation that is being described and what is termed “social insanity” in fact reveals that reading-while-walking is sane in contrast to the political and social tensions that rule the city. Middle sister, in her defiance of the communal rules, sets an example for the possibilities of individual walking carving a route for self-determined acts and experiences.

Furthermore, her “social insanity”, I suggest, is her “walking herself free”, evading the restraints by entering a zone that is referred to as “beyond the pale”. As Drong explains in his discussion of boundaries in *Milkman* “the phrase ‘beyond the pale’ came to be synonymous with anything unruly, wild, unacceptable, outside agreed standards of decency” (Drong)⁷. Furthermore, going beyond the pale symbolizes a transgression of social codes that are denominated by the community (cf. Drong). Again, it is her brother-in-law, who makes this clear to middle-sister:

‘Yes. Those books’, he said. ‘And that walking’, and he started in from another angle, this time the angle of how, if I wasn’t careful I’d be banished to the furthest reaches of darkness, ostracized and shown no mercy as a district beyond-the-pale. Already he warned that I was being talked about as the ‘reading-while-walking’ person. (63)

It is interesting to note that the walking individual is referred to as a district beyond-the-pale. And the irony (or perhaps tragedy) lies in the fact that walking through the city that one is raised in, and is most familiar with, can lead to being cast out of that native and well-known territory. The “darkness” as her brother-in-law terms it in this excerpt is what lies beyond the socially acceptable but it is also the territory itself that is thus divided into the known and the unfamiliar, the home and the unhomey.

Here we can see the difference between urban walking as the disengaged observation by the figure of the flâneur. And the rag-picker whose movement through the city is more precarious and potentially dangerous. The flâneur remains at a safe distance and the rag-picker is entangled and enmeshed in the shadier parts of the city. Middle sister, by reading-while-walking resists the rules of conformity, becomes a site of unknown darkness of the district “beyond-the-pale” herself.

Even though the protagonist is ostracized and marginalized by the watchful community and despite the warning that is issued by her brother-in-law, she persists in reading-while-walking and from this place of beyond-the-pale she re-writes the city’s dividing lines and challenges the existence of restricted areas. By inhabiting the space of

⁷ Drong expounds in more detail: “The pale in the phrase refers to a fence of pointed stakes; also used in a figurative sense of a limit, a boundary, a restriction (Online Etymology Dictionary, s.v). Interestingly, by employing the ‘beyond the pale’ phrase, middle sister seems to replicate Irish-English divisions within her own nationalist community. Also, by reading while walking, and by refusing to accept reality as it is (by escaping into earlier centuries and into fictions by XIX c. – and earlier – writers), she trespasses within her own community’s symbolic territory. She demonstrates, simultaneously, that the nationalist community in Seventies Ardoyne (reputed to have been one of the most united and determined to fight for the republican ideals) is far from uniform and disciplined” (Drong).

the outcast, she makes it possible to cross the boundaries of a deeply divided society. As Sales expounds in her work on *The Troubles*:

[...] the separation and alienation of Protestants and Catholics became part of everyday experience. Politics has centred around community loyalties, giving little space for alternative agendas. (Sales 3)

Her walking is a mode of re-writing the spatial and political divisions of the city, of the community and, by implication, of the nation. Walking as a discursive practice also substitutes the need to control the spatial boundaries and the activities that are either taking place within or beyond the circumscribed territories of the conflicting parties. As becomes clear in her own reflection on her stubborn habit of walking:

I knew that by reading while I walked I was losing touch in a crucial sense with communal up-to-dateness and that that, indeed, was risky. It was important to be in the know, to keep up with, especially when things here got added on to at much a price compound rate. On the other hand, being up on, having awareness, clocking everything - both rumour and actuality - didn't prevent things from happening or allow for intervention, or reversal of things that had already happened. Knowledge didn't guarantee power, safety and relief [...]. (65)

Middle sister correctly assumes that her knowledge of the city's shady activities does not guarantee her safety from terror and harm that could potentially happen to her while she makes herself vulnerable by reading-while-walking. Foucault's maxim of knowledge as power does not apply in this situation. Instead, by the narrator's decision not to be "in the know", she produces an alternative to the conformity of the citizens of her town. At the same time, her wandering about without constant observation and without the knowledge of what is going on in the streets, implies that she does not depend on, and does not succumb to, the rules and restrictions that the political situation imposed on the community.

Another consequence of wandering about without observation and knowledge is that she becomes vulnerable to the advances of the milkman. The milkman stands for male aggression in times of crisis, where there is no protection from law enforcement or from vigilant citizenry. In the strained climate of *The Troubles*, the threat from the milkman is even more intense as it remains unclear which party he represents and what his true allegiance is. Thus, middle sister also would be unable to identify the parties to turn to for protection. What complicates matters even more, is that her defiance of gender roles - she rejects the marriage options her mother suggests - and her walking as another form of "unfeminine" behaviour make her even more suspect in the eyes of the community. She is thought to have provoked or even encouraged the milkman's interest in her. In this seemingly inescapable situation her insistence on walking is truly courageous. Her first response to the milkman is this:

Anyway, I did not want a lift. That was generally speaking. I liked walking - walking and reading, walking and thinking. Also, specifically speaking, I did not want to get in the car with this man. (3)

The pursuit of the milkman, who is considerably older than her, married and probably a paramilitary whose activities are inherently obscure, is thwarted at first by her choice of

walking even if he offers her a lift. She turns down this offer of a powerful and menacing man and keeps up with her uninhibited practice of walking. The gendered difference between women walking and men walking, as mentioned earlier, is not just the difference between the flâneur and the rag-picker, but it is crucial in this situation where the choice is between walking alone and accepting a lift that is even more intimidating. It seems that her option of walking is not less perilous but it is her individual choice, her personal determination.

The streets in the novel *Milkman* are not a safe public place where people get together freely and easily. On the contrary, the streets are unsafe, high-risk areas. Therefore, it seems rather unlikely that someone would choose to walk those streets to gain personal freedom or express one's will and agency. Solnit, on the other hand, points out that "[w]alking the streets is what links up reading the map with living one's life, the personal microcosm with the public macrocosm; it makes sense of the maze all around" (Solnit 177). If middle sister establishes this link between her walking and the macrocosm of the social environment, she forces a re-consideration of the meaning of walking. Her walking is not just risky or reckless; rather, it needs to be viewed as a commitment to the street, to the public re-instatement of her right to be a vulnerable citizen. Thus, she insists on the pedestrian lifestyle: "Every weekday, rain or shine, gunplay or bombs. Stamp-off or riots, I preferred to walk home reading my latest book" (5).

As has become apparent, Anna Burns's *Milkman* illustrates the meaning of walking in times of crisis. Walking is a committed choice to individual freedom made manifest in the public sphere. Gender norms do not apply here, as the protagonist rejects appropriate feminine roles and insists on her right to walk in the middle of disturbance and danger. Warnings that are being voiced by her relatives do not impede her desire to read and walk. Despite the fact that she is made vulnerable by being oblivious to the potential perilousness of the streets. The actual threats of violence and injury as well as the riskiness of being a social outcast by going beyond-the-pale are obvious to the protagonist, and yet, she remains firm in her decision to walk.

Walking, in Macaulay's study, can "pose a challenge to social tendencies that accentuate forms of domestication or domination". He firmly asks to strive for a greater "understanding the dynamic and democratic dimensions of walking", and thus to "begin to interrogate and critically contest the opaque and authoritarian features of urban architecture, private property and public space" (Macaulay). With more social connectedness to our close environment, to the urban landscape and to the city's walkable places, we might eventually, start to re-organise our very social structure and life patterns⁸. Today, we are neither disengaged flâneurs nor marginal rag-pickers, but we are certainly re-claiming the walking areas in our cities. What follows logically is that we might demand a re-consideration of the urban designs and distribution of public spaces so that we obtain equal rights and opportunities to walk our cities. In Anna Burns' *Milkman*,

⁸ Equally, Solnit claims that there is a vital connection between the experience of walking, the places that one walks in and social life: "In great cities, spaces as well as places are designed and built: walking, witnessing, being in public, are as much part of the design and purpose as is being inside to eat, sleep, make shoes or love or music. The word *citizen* has to do with cities, and the ideal city is organized around citizenship—around participation in public life" (Solnit 176).

the protagonist consciously chooses to be vulnerable on the streets and neither being a social outcast nor proving a likely victim for the milkman deters her from walking as a favourite means of transport and movement. The novel thus makes it rather clear that walking can be a conscious decision in the midst of a crisis. It is precisely the vulnerability of middle sister that inspires a greater engagement with the actual urban and social environment that one is placed in. In her case, she must endure the restrictions of a divided community; we in times of a global pandemic, on the other hand, have to tolerate restrictions far less oppressive than those. Hopefully, walking helps on a daily basis, to re-charge and re-connect, and, in the long term, stimulate democratic changes of our urban habitat.

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